

SUMMARY OF THE IMPACT OF A NON-FICTION, LOW BUDGET, DIGITAL SOCIAL MEDIA PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

This summary includes a synopsis of a 5-year social media exploratory project: non-fiction Facebook advert plus a literature review to support the dissemination of the results relating to the technique and the theme of 'making digital work'.

A digital marketing strategy ideally should incorporate a range of methods and budgets (qualitative and quantitative in design) and this has been an aim of this work. To summarise, the 'reach' of 26 Facebook posts (this included adverts and social messages: organic and non-organic design) for an approximate £50.00 budget resulted in 6,239 people (reach/saw the advert) outside of Britain. The impact is the primary data 'reach' results for this project. Collectively, by 2024, the primary and secondary methods provided a result of 86,860 findings.

KEYWORDS

consumer science, solo travel, emotional and business intelligence, GPS nonorganic Facebook advert, primary quantitative data

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital advertising provides an opportunity to reach people and companies around the world. As a **small business owner**, the marketing strategy is designed, implemented and reviewed as part of the quarterly and annual business review. A **social media, digital marketing strategy** ideally should incorporate a range of methods and budgets. The project was launched in 2017 and a summary report completed in 2024. One exploratory method was a 5-year project which was launched in 2017, and completed in 2022, to assess one method of advertising [a service]: **an advert**. The methodology section includes more details of the primary and secondary tasks and techniques implemented and completed.

The main aspect of the project was inspired by previous conversations with older EFL (English as a Foreign Language or ESOL) students *who were worried about their future holiday options as 'solo travellers' and the need to keep costs down within an already limited budget*. This also links to the 'ageing society' (retirement concerns and well-being) and the Visitor Economy (hospitality and tourism). The theme 'not wanting to be alone in a new city' was chosen for this project.

1.1. Making Digital Work - Knowledge Transfer - Non-Fiction

How can this exploratory research be disseminated/published for knowledge transfer purposes? The 'impact results' provide insight into a potentially **cost-efficient method** of using a social media application. Social media research projects help us to identify both trends and

opportunities in the digital world. This then allows us to review and plan within the concepts of **social geography** together with **social and human capital** and in doing so we can develop our **business intelligence** and **emotional intelligence**. The author [for researcher ethics and responsible practise] wants to publish this exploratory project (the procedure, method and outputs). The author has completed research reports in the past that relate to digital infrastructure developments [for child and families] in specific socially deprived areas and some of this work is cited in this paper (to support relevant aspects as detailed in the next section: literature review). The author declares that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Prior to the development of the digital, social media industry, a **marketing strategy** would have focused on the costs and impact of a phone or letter service. Receiving an email, as opposed to a phone call or posted letter was a new and exciting option with the launch and implementation of a digital information technology (IT) system. This enabled a company to **reach and engage with** more potential customers in a quicker timescale regardless of the **proximity** of either parties. Consequently, the success of this email option service became more **cost-efficient based on speed** and the volume of information (by quantity: size & shape considered, for instance) shared compared to a phonecall or posted letter (when the customer had an IT system that was compatible and able to receive the email). The shift from customer to consumer needs and interests was a key part of this communication exchange. This enabled the concept of ‘**consumer science**’ to continue to evolve (and in many corporate, large businesses and industries) into partnership and stakeholder/shareholder working.

Digital advertising provides an opportunity to reach people and companies around the world. Targeting a particular location (as a technique to test ‘reach’) using an application that utilises the **global positioning system (GPS)** was planned for this 5-year exploratory project. An article in the ITNow Magazine 2019 [1] details an interview with Brad Parkinson who was part of the team that were awarded the Queen Elizabeth Engineering prize for creating the revolutionary GPS: **GPS has the ability to pinpoint a location exactly in space and time.**

Receiving brief information (like a postcard) can evoke interest in finding out more about a particular destination and therefore, a small message sent digitally (with hyperlinks that can provide more information quickly) must be instantly interesting to the receiver. Some studies have focused on **postcards** and have confirmed this positive outcome. One 2006 study [2] applied a variety of **data analysis tests** (i.e. frequency distribution, mean and standard deviations, reliability tests, series of pair-wise sample *t* tests, independent regression) and reported:

Two regression analyses were run to test the relationship between the dependent (postcard-induced desire to travel) and independent variables (postcard-induced emotions)..The associations between induced emotions and desire to travel were strong in both cases. It appears that emotions would predict 0.64 of the variance in desire to travel [2]

I certainly agree with their statement that if executed properly, information and images relayed through postcards can have promotional value and this **emotional and business intelligence** can be completely relevant to a **digital social media advert**. Another **holiday/tourism study** involved a **meta analysis** of 87 papers (from 246) and the 2020 results were similar: a visual of the destination had the greatest impact [3].

A **pop-up banner style advert**, however, can be negatively described as a *relentless nuisance* when you're focused on reading online. These are non-organic (paid adverts). This of course, has been formally reported as well as discussed more casually amongst friends and family (outside of a formal, scheduled feedback/evaluative/research type task). Online marketing can be *irritating* for some social media users (the **consumers**) and a 2023 study of 335 participants provided evidence of this [4]. Other negative responses were *social media advertising is confusing, deceptive, annoying and too insistent*. The main results of this study however, did find that **brand awareness** positively impacts purchase intention among **online consumers**. The study designed a purposive sample of people over 18 years of age, who were active on Facebook as well as a range of other social media platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, Snapchat, Metaverse and internet forums. *They recommend further research to understand demotivator variables like irritation or annoyance*. The study is published in the online journal: Journal of Social Media in Society. It's a blind peer-reviewed, open-access, online journal that accepts scholarly articles and book reviews. The journal is devoted to scholarship and commentary on social media and its impact on society. It has a 'search' facility but unlike other online resources it doesn't give an indication of the resulting number of papers/articles/books/publications. In 2024, it does indicate there are journals available to search from 2012-2023: 24 volumes with between 5-18 publications in each so a potential total of approx 250 (200-300) publications. The author hasn't verified these 2024 results for accuracy, validity and relevance.

A [secondary data] search on the Taylor Francis Group website <https://www.tandfonline.com>: **non-organic social media advert** resulted in 15,279 articles. The author hasn't verified these results for accuracy, validity and relevance. However, one of these articles [5] focused on regular media (not online/offline: TV, Magazine, Newspaper) and organic Facebook social media adverts. This relates to consumer/customer loyalty and developing/maintaining trust and/or interest. Their results give insights into:

time-series analysis for the influence of offline media on organic Facebook reach, viral reach, and page likes: immediate and the long-term effects of offline media expenditures on viral reach [5]

The research found that **established [offline] consumers** were more positive and active as Facebook followers for the same companies/products. So prior trust, fostered more online positive activity. Developing a customer database to either phone and/or send a letter (via Royal mail) to existing or potential customers used to be an important aspect for most company marketing departments. Understanding customers and what they want, developing loyalty and trust are all important aspects for business success. **Data storage** is a continual dilemma (alongside ethical guidelines) for the safety and reliability of its purpose. There's been many authors that have focused on the research, development and progress of data storage. A 2019 [6] article focused on this and included information on public, private and hybrid clouds as well as the futuristic undersea micro-data centers. Some social media services have provided designs that allow people to 'follow' without the requirement to exchange personal details (addresses, bank details, etc) which can eliminate the need for customer databases. Regardless of this, **storage** for historical message recall is still desirable because it can help track and develop customer relationships.

How can 'reach' be converted into real customers and at what cost? Researchers have been exploring this (for business marketing purposes) by focusing on consumers' online shopping behaviour as reported in 2013 [7]. Four new types of **social media consumers** were identified and they applied this classification in their work with their own newly formed variables. Table 1, is a summary of their classification.

Table 1: Classifying online consumers for marketing efficiency adapted from Simona Vinerean, Iuliana Cetina, Luigi Dumitrescu & Mihai Tichindelean 2013 research findings [7]

4 Types of social media consumers	New variables for social media consumers	continuous variables	categorical variables
Engagers Expressers and Informers Networkers Watchers and Listeners	Positive reactions to online ads Trust in information from personal sources Trust in information from foreign sources	Concern for privacy Importance of social media	Experience using social media Clicking the ad Log in pattern Timespent per login session

This type of research has increased the knowledge base of ‘**consumer science**’. The researchers concluded:

following the general idea that segmentation can leverage a better understanding of consumers' behavior, in order to obtain the desired effect of any marketing activity.....to achieve a segmentation of social media users and observe different patterns which could be targeted to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of online marketing activities [7]

With the rise of online anti-social, unwanted/not requested, abusive and other negative experiences, there’s a revival of **business intelligence** training to assist businesses in understanding their customers (or potential customer base). Business Marketing specialists are trained to understand the **boundaries of customer care** (particularly for cold-calling direct sales work or working with a customer database) agreeing scheduled contact phone-calls, emails or posted letters, for instance, and when to stop contacting them. Online advertising can be managed depending on the social media application design and cost efficiency (of organic and non-organic advertng). Although, there has been a focus on supporting all people (of all ages and ability) to be more **digitally confident users** (so training to understand how to deal with unwanted adverts, for instance). Behaviour, attitude and the language we use online tends to be slightly different to appeal to a range of consumers. Many established organisations already embed values, ground rules, code of conduct, privacy and customer care guidelines and expectations in their work place. ‘*Consumer Science*’ findings and online **review website services** (like TrustPilot, Google reviews, company website reviews) support transparency and openness regardless as to whether they are public or private businesses and this has challenged some aspects of privacy and loyalty (for both customers, colleagues and owners).

Teams and/or customers experience *irritation, dissatisfaction, disappointment* and consequently will share negativeness in their communication - this can be direct or indirectly (so not related to the current situation, hence, just any opportunity) to express their irritation. Critical constructive feedback in the workplace is part of the support system. The purpose of this feedback system is to allow workers to reflect and develop their **business intelligence skills**. However, when communication within a business is ‘**toxic**’ and personal anger management support isn’t available or not managed professionally, relationships change and a **toxic ‘group think’ culture** can develop. Equal opportunities, workers rights and human/citizenship rights can be challenged and damaged and result in **unfairness, discrimination and hate communication** styles rise and

become the norm. A business can lose customers, become **unprofitable** and closure can be the only option. Customer care during this is often comprised and tested. In 2023, the Centre for Countering Digital Hate: CCDH [8], was awarded for their work. This is a not-for-profit, non-governmental organization (NGO) that is funded by philanthropic trusts and members of the public. Their mission is to protect human rights and civil liberties online and has legal support (Global Summit 2022) in the United States of America, the European Union, the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia and New Zealand. In 2024, a search for research articles on their website resulted in 47 published articles. One of the research reports: Public Support for Social Media Reform, '*shows that the majority of people in the US are tired of being exploited by social media companies and want governments and platforms to address **online hate and disinformation***'. The research is based on responses from both adults and 13-17 year olds in America (1,010 adults and 1,012 of the younger age group sampled). One of the results showed that:

American teens, particularly those with high social media use, have considerably higher levels of belief in a range of conspiracy theories, including antisemitic and white supremacist propaganda, than adults [8]

The terminology included in this report details safety by design, transparency, accountability and responsibility. This approach for **social media regulation**, if implemented, could also help to improve confidence, trust and safety for **digital consumers**. It will involve *changing corporate behaviour* for social media and **search engine companies**.

Dealing with toxic or deprived or disadvantaged people, groups and communities is the work of sociologists, economists and social geographers. Understanding that people have **barriers to resources** (in urban and rural locations) has been a focus for many social scientists and governments over the last 50 years [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14,15,16,17 & 18]. The British Dyslexia Association, for instance, have continually engaged in research to develop **resources** that help children, and adults, access education (so remove barriers) and be successful in their learning. The author of this report contributed to dyslexia research in the 1990's. The digital industry and **knowledge transfer systems** have supported the training of teachers in England in being more aware of learning challenges like dyslexia. The British Dyslexia Association now has an active social media service including a FaceBook service and a website: www.bdadyslexia.org.uk[15]. There's also the MadeByDyslexia charity: www.madebydyslexia.org[16] which has digital services including a dyslexia assessment which can be accessed on a mobile smartphone or other **digital (computerised) devices**. The British Dyslexia organisation has also focused on numerical complications and challenges specific to the problem of **dyscalculia** and the learning and remembering of simple mathematics. The '*fear of maths*' is a common characteristic of people with **dyscalculia** and this becomes more of a problem with **personal finance** planning in later years escalating into further difficulties which then result in affecting their ability to be **normal consumers**.

In 2006, a National Evaluation of Sure Start (NESS) publications <http://www.ness.bbk.ac.uk> (relating to children centres and 3-year old children, in specific known deprived areas in England) also contributed to the digital world. It concluded, the fact that **socio-economics** were found to be linked with **diet deficiencies**. As a Research Fellow and Regional Support Office for the National Evaluation of Sure Start team, the author supported 80 programmes with technical support for their local evaluation responsibilities as required by the government. **Digital connectivity** was a major part of this work for all involved. *To summarise, households with the lowest levels of household incomes (at the time of the research, these were Sure Start Children Centre locations) had the higher rates of obesity, for instance, compared to children from*

households with the highest levels of income [17]. This 2006 report detailed the World Health Organisation (WHO) findings of the prevalence of **obesity** among children aged 2-10 years old. They had risen between 1995 and 2003! Hence, a 4% rise from 10% to 14% in an 8 year period. However, the largest rise was 6% (children aged 8-10). The rise in **childhood obesity** at this time, was seen as a precursor to less favourable health status in later life, as well as having more immediate negative impacts on the child (reminiscent of the health problems of England in William Shakespeare's lifetime). These outcomes challenged the concept of social capital, human capital, human geography, social geography, **business intelligence and emotional intelligence** alongside sociological explanations and theories of individuals and communities [17].

Some Sure Start programmes provided an integrated and holistic approach to young mothers by providing Teenage Breakfast Clubs [17]. These had previously shown to be popular for emotional and peer support to **socially isolated young mothers**. In theory, this was a good example of embracing the concept of **social capital** (participating in a social group with other young mothers) with the potential to increase their **human capital** (invest and gain knowledge to improve their capacity to become productive members of society: developing a work ethic, supporting employability, tackling worklessness) and in doing so improve their **emotional intelligence**. This work included providing technology to tackle these type of previously know 'hard to reach' families. Computers, Ipads and mobile phones were allocated to help **reach, engage with,** support and motivate these families, hence encouraging the development of **digital skills** for these communities. This required the Sure Start workers to develop their **business intelligence** to be successful. The NESS 2006 Cost Effectiveness report provided more insight into the work of Sure Start with a few examples of how the work was evaluated [18].

More recently, an article in ITNow (June 2019) explained how the '**digital skills gap**' was a focus for financial employees who were mentoring inner city children: 'Bank staff help inner city kids master computer science' [19]. This 2019 focus on inner city as a location is reminiscent of widely known social deprivation factors. I made recommendations between 2004-2006 to Sure Start programmes that **shadowing** opportunities (a way of working) for parents should be implemented and evaluated to support their future **employability** (as once the child/family credit payment/government income ceases they will need an income to be financially healthy). This recommendation was made based on the concepts of **human and social capital** plus **business and emotional intelligence** matters. These Sure Start mothers met once a week to cook and eat a healthy breakfast whilst offering peer support to each other including on issues such as parenting. Hence, some Sure Start programmes provided new services for local communities as well as enhance those existing ones. Both integrated and more specific activities for **nutrition support** were implemented where there appeared to be a gap in services [17, 18]. There was very little evidence of **shadowing** or similar supportive work for parents, or people living in the local area or community, in the local evaluation reports.

Shadowing and **mentoring** work has been reviewed continually over the years and some of this has been symbiotic, with the digital industry sector [20,21]. A 2021 article focused on understanding the role of the mentee and how to be a mentee [21]. The NESS Nutrition 2006 report [17], included examples of some of the educational approaches to support childrens' **healthy eating** such as **cooking, horticultural projects and dental hygiene and oral health** and the online publications detail more specific information on this. This nutrition work was delivered by a range of staff who had developed an understanding of the cultural and socioeconomics of the local community and the family needs (so they had gained **business intelligence** for their roles which can be linked to more recent (2019) discussions [22, 23] where the focus is **customer/consumer needs** in the digital world. Sure Start mothers were supported

with problems such as managing a typical food intolerance (i.e. dairy food intolerance). So providing 'non-dairy meals' support including buying 'non-dairy products' (on a limited family budget) which is still relevant today regardless of age and health. So ideal for **ageing society** and **well-being** themes.

The NESS work (2000-2006) was able to include the different types of families in England (as opposed to other parts of Britain) by marriage status, age, disability, ethnicity and **religious/belief** status. The data showed that the families identified mainly as *monotheistic (Christian/Catholic, Muslim, Sikhism) and some polytheism (Hinduism, Buddhism) and no religion*. Based on this data and the ethnicity data collected, it was clear that some of the Sure Start programmes needed to be able to support large ethnic minority families and communities with differing religious beliefs. The relationship between food and some religious (or beliefs) groups is widely understood, for example, some beliefs restrict certain foods and others follow a particular diet (this can include particular meals, food preparation and/ or the timing of meals). Vegetarianism is a popular diet for many adults. Some meat is prohibited in some groups like Hinduism, Jainism, Muslim and Buddhism. Vegan diets are also popular. Parents with **food intolerances or allergies** also needed to increase their own knowledge of these, follow a particular diet to avoid foods that irritate, and trigger, their problems whilst planning to also alleviate any future health risks (due to a specific diet). **Digital technology** in these deprived areas enabled these parents to start to complete their own research and plan appointments to manage these important family nutrition essentials.

In the wider English communities, families still identify as those religious or belief faiths previously mentioned as well as Judaism, Paganism and smaller populations such as Alevi, Jain, Wicca, Ravidassia, Shamanism, Rastafarian and Zoroastrian as detailed in the 2021 census www.ons.gov.uk report [24]. Atheist, Agnostic or Humanists beliefs were recorded as 'any other' or non-religious group preferences. There are also some people that identify as multi-faith or interfaith groups (such as Baha'I'). **Digital technology** has enabled this community information to be collected, stored and considered for service development for children and families (from birth and through to ageing society needs).

The NESS [17, 18] health publications detailed numerous themes relating to antenatal and postnatal nutrition services including information on the variety of different ethnic backgrounds of children living in Sure Start areas and the **range of languages** used and the **multidisciplinary teams** involved. Over 800 documents were analysed and a grounded theory approach together with 'content analysis' was used to handle and sort a wide variety of documents and information. This is similar to a **meta-analysis** style of working such as the Cochrane Collaboration systematic reviews. The data has been used for wider data set analysis and developing children services social policy. This has enabled the **digital word [computer science industry]** to develop systems for data storage, data monitoring and analysis (including **algorithm tasks**) to assist in the management of public (and private) service related problems. The NESS topics included disability; deaf families; teenage pregnancy; social, emotional, cognitive and health aspects for young children; well-being; employability; cost effectiveness and cost benefit; hard to reach families; multi-disciplinary childcare practitioners/teams.

The National Evaluation of Sure Start (NESS) was a multifaceted investigation to illuminate the effects of Sure Start, as well as the conditions under which, and the mechanisms, by which it exerts its impact. The context of the work (both the Sure Start services and NESS) links with the hierarchy themes of **human and social capital**, and **human geography**. What the **integrated cross-sectional, longitudinal** project had to consider was:

- (a) *the geographic, demographic, and ethnic nature of Sure Start communities, including their **relative levels of deprivation and social exclusion**,*
- (b) *strategies proposed by each community for implementing Sure Start in their original funding applications,*
- (c) *their early success in implementing Sure Start*

The NESS literature is still relevant today due to its focus on children, families and communities. A 2024 google search re: **Social geography** [25] resulted in the following concise statement:

Social geography is the branch of human geography that explores the relationships between society and space. It focuses on the spatial variation and processes related to social aspects of everyday life. Socialgeography examines divisions within society, including class, ethnicity, religion, gender, sexual orientation, and age. [25]

Digital working has enabled a pragmatic style of working with **outcomes that are often easily measurable within a particular timescale**. So where are the 3-year old children now (the Sure Start cohort)? and did their families breakout of the deprivation/poverty lifestyle? Or did they as adults?

The author of this report, studied ‘**distant learning pedagogy**’ in the 1990’s and the OU (Open University) system which was established in 1969. So a long time before the launch of the Sure Start work. The creation and launch of the digital industry has enabled the ‘**distant learning pedagogy**’ **model of education** to be successful as it has embraced proximity challenges and opportunities over the years as part of its business education working model. Over time, the **internet computer network system** has enabled its use for social media applications and these have also become less expensive as more **consumers** engage with the system.

A secondary data research project was published in 2021 [26] that involved analysing (using the snowballing technique) 88 papers to identify the different **definitions of social media**. The result was 21 original definitions of social media. The researchers found that after further analysis of the 21 definitions, there was a **lexical density**:

i.e. the percentage of nouns, adjectives, verbs, and adverbs of 57.5 percent. The most frequently used word with 23 occurrences is ‘social’; people with 12 occurrences is ‘virtual’, ‘content’, ‘user’, and ‘network’ had 8 occurrences each. In terms of two-word phrases, social network[s]: 8 occurrences; social media: 5 occurrences; social networking: 5 occurrences; virtual communities: 4 occurrences. [26]

This secondary research was able to track the terminology changes over time. Initially, ‘virtual communities’ was used and later ‘social media’ became more accepted. This research was completed by an Italian team of which would have been interested in the **linguistics** of this **developing digital industry**. A study was published in 2019 [27] where the researchers analysed 4391 published journal articles and this resulted in 1142 of these articles (in 12 journals) being related to the topic of **social media**. Their work provides some robust explanations of social science **quantitative and qualitative** methods, and techniques, that have been reported in communication articles. They found:

nearly half of the articles (42.8 %) were authored by the USA and the articles were mostly published by Human Communication Research Journal (9.7%). USA authors published the highest number articles in the highest IF journals. Following the USA, UK authors published most of the articles in these 10 journals. Fourth, Italian, Chinese and Germans collaborated more than 3 authors. USA and Netherland authored articles cited more than the other country authors while the least cited paper was authored by China [27]

These social media research projects help us to identify both trends and opportunities in the digital world. This then allows us to review and plan within the concepts of **social geography** together with **social and human capital** interests and objectives-they provide the wider contextual framework for the work of social scientists.

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for this exploratory project included primary and secondary data collection using both qualitative and quantitative methods. The design and data collection equipment used for this project was a mobile smartphone - internet/online wifi- **digital connection**. The report was written on a laptop computer. The timescale for the data collection was:

- primary data was collected over 5 years (2017 to 2022)
- secondary data was collected over 2 years (2022 to 2024)

The *budget for an advert* was the main focus for this digital marketing project and a social media 'Facebook page' was created to explore the design of an advert, its cost and the impact of it over a particular timescale (to generate primary, quantitative data, results). The Facebook application was chosen due to its design - it included the GPS technology which had the ability to target a specific geographic location. The main research question was, *is a social media advert a cost-efficient method for a small business?*

This exploratory project included testing the procedure and impact of 2 different Facebook methods as well as adding information (to an old advert) by raising/posting messages in the 'message feed/comments section'. Adverts of organic and non-organic design were included. After the launch of the project, an analysis of the impact of the adverts was made available by the Facebook Meta Business software system (Ads Manager service). This application enabled the GPS technology to be utilised with 'geographical targeted' Facebook adverts and then an analysis/interpretation of the results. The target audience for the non-organic advert was older adults (male and female) , aged over 35 years and the location was Kazakhstan.

The main theme for this social media project was inspired by conversations with older EFL (English as a Foreign Language or ESOL) students *who were worried about their future holiday options as 'solo travellers' and the need to keep costs down within an already limited budget*. The theme 'not wanting to be alone in a new city' was chosen for this project. The author is experienced in hospitality work.

Primary qualitative data was [informally] considered during conversations with students [and not recorded] this was reflected on by the author and informed the research design of this exploratory project. The quantitative data was collected from a social media 'marketing/advertising' advert. Secondary data was collected for the literature review and 27

references have been cited. This secondary data included hard-copy publications as well as online publications. One hard-copy publication contained 7 relevant articles and these have been cited in the literature review section. A google search using specific key words was completed for some of the secondary data searches and resulted in 6 online sources being relevant.

4. SUMMARY OF RESULTS

This summary includes the overall results of the primary and secondary data collections. Collectively, there were 86,860 results and these will be briefly summarised in this section.

Firstly, the secondary data, digital search resulted overall in 80,621 papers being potentially relevant from 6 on-line publication websites (these 6 were the outcome of an initial Google search). The specific results are shown in Table 2. The author hasn't verified any of the specific literature for accuracy, validity and relevance (this was the result of a Google search).

Secondly, the primary data 'reach result' of 26 posts (this included adverts and social messages: organic and non-organic design) for a £50.00 (GBP: British sterling) budget resulted in 6,239 people (reach/saw the advert) outside of Britain. 6,239 people saw the advert and these people were located in Germany and Kazakhstan (where the adverts were designed to be seen). The author decided to focus on the primary results relating to Kazakhstan only, for this paper.

Table 2. Secondary data results

6 Website sources	Key words search	Results (80,621)	Classification of results on the website
https://www.academia.edu	non-organic social media advert	60,000 papers	7,352 text papers 64 videos 20 courses
Taylor Francis Group https://www.tandfonline.com	non-organic social media advert	15,279 articles	N/A
International Journal of Lifelong Education Taylor Francis Group https://www.tandfonline.com	social and human capital	652	N/A
Sage Journal https://journals.sagepub.com/	human geography	4,643	N/A
Centre for Countering Digital Hate: CCDH counterhate.com	Social media advert	47	N/A
Journal of Social Media in Society thejsms.org	Non-organic advert	N/A	N/A

Within the total of this 6,239 'reach' result was one advert (a non-organic design which cost £13.00) which had a 12-day duration schedule, and a 'reach' result of 4,408. The reach results cost per link engagement, therefore, was £0.08. 52.5% of the 4,408 reach were women in Kazakhstan and 47.5% of the 4,408 reach were men in Kazakhstan. Based on this result, a **digital connection** was made with a university and embassy in Kazakhstan [this can be interpreted as an 'impact' result].

5. CONCLUSION

The Facebook Meta Business software system (Ads Manager service) provided more insight into the impact of the social media adverts. It also assisted with the management and creation of adverts for mobile smartphone use: mobile adverts. Reflecting on the results, more questions were raised such as, are there potential customers waiting in Kazakhstan? Can the Facebook Meta Business software system help to develop business outcomes for small businesses? How can the 'reach' result of a Facebook advert be interpreted? The primary data 'reach' result showed that 4,408 people saw the advert in Kazakhstan but how 'active' were these 4,408 people in reading the information in the advert? Did they need to translate the information? Does the lexical language framework need to be developed? Was the translation accurate? Did they tell their friends, family and colleagues about the advert? Or did it just passively 'reach' their Facebook page? What percentage of people in this country have access to and use the Facebook application? What percentage of people in Kazakhstan trust this digital service? What business relationships can be developed? In 2021, the population of Kazakhstan was 19 million according to a Google 2024 search and 6 people were reported to be billionaires in a March 2024 list. Are they digitally connected? Is there social deprivation in this country that affects their **digital experience**?

The secondary data findings, for instance, found that established [offline] **consumers** were more positive and active as Facebook followers for the same companies/products. So prior trust, fostered more online positive activity. How can these results inform relatively new company business strategies? Or is it more appropriate for established and accomplished businesses to develop aspects of the work to develop online **consumer confidence**?

The **distant learning pedagogy** (online learning regardless of proximity to the school, college or university) was challenged and in real life, consequently, was tested for its use, reliability and value during the **COVID-19 pandemic** months. As people, globally, have gained access to the internet, and learnt about a variety of topics, are they now able to visit and/or have holidays in different parts of world if they choose to? Will they travel with their friends, families or are they confident to travel 'solo'? Often, it's just not convenient to travel with family or friends and people travel solo to resolve this personal dilemma (when they feel confident to do so).

The exploratory social media project was designed, launched and reviewed on a small budget. The themes link to the 'ageing society', retirement concerns, well-being and the Visitor Economy.

The **distant learning pedagogy** is a remarkable educational concept and the impact of this is being monitored and reviewed throughout many countries and continents as part of **COVID Recovery** working. Many organisations have evolved as part of the digital industry success such as digital help and support services; educational services; media engineering design and publication; business intelligence; **customer satisfaction**; on-line shopping; quality assurance online; website storage; safety and safeguarding. This industry has been dependant on independent problem solving workers who can also be helpful team workers. The secondary data results demonstrate the quantity of digitally published information using a small selection of key words relevant to this project. Hence, the scope for more research within this is needed to ensure that the **existing knowledge is utilised** (prior to any unnecessary and costly primary data collection). Managing information overload has consequently been an important aspect for **educators** and business leaders to prepare and plan for - to support the '**well-being**' and its workers, peers, colleagues, mentees and students. The consequence of information overload is **stress** - another **stressor**! Educators and business leaders have had to review and develop their **emotional intelligence** as part of the **COVID-19 pandemic and COVID Recovery** years.

Mentoring services have been an important part of this style of working (helping others to manage their stressors whilst being productive).

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